

Original Research Article

Teaching Parts of Speech through Literature: An Experiment

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Abstract

It is a study of the parts of speech through literature which are influential for the achievement of the students. For this purpose, an experiment was conducted to find out the difference between control group and experimental group. In this study selected the control group and experimental group of 8th class in HITEC Boys High School Taxilla Cantt on the basis of pre-test. The control group was treated as usual after pre-test and experimental group was treated through literature. After delivering the model lessons, a post-test was conducted from two groups. The post test was developed for the collection of data for this study. It was consisted of forty items i.e. MCQs, true false, fill in the blanks' and matching items ten items of each types. The test covered the first five parts of speech and eight items of each type was included. T-test technique was used for testing the significance of the statements at $\alpha = .05$ significance level. Result of the post test was compared in order to identify findings draw conclusions and suggest recommendations. Bar chart was used for the comparison of the control group and experimental group.

Keyword: Experimental group, Literature, Parts of speech

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INTRODUCTION

It is said that the study of literature 'begins in delight and ends in wisdom' and it is true for an EFL / ESL, students of English as it is for native speakers. Over the last few years use of new methodologies and technologies have effective role in teaching in the modern era. Traditional and typical methods are no more in use, so different techniques and material are used to exploit students' response especially in teaching of English grammar. Since last decade the role of literature has increased in language class whereas it was considered as useless. But now as the pendulum has swung the other way, literature is considered as an integral part of any language-teaching program.

The inclusion of literature in language teaching, for example, can bring a fresh breeze into the dry and mechanical task of language learning. Grammar teaching is a tedious and boring job and a fairly long process.

Literature can make grammar teaching enjoyable because it does not provide a genuine text only but it also gives pleasure by engaging emotions. Therefore, it motivates and stimulates the language learner.

In concrete terms, many of the writers suggest that it would improve linguistic awareness and grasp of the mother tongue. The struggle for accuracy in grammar and idiom would help to form enduring habits of careful thought. As another view, English is important as we have so often called it a window to the outside world. Report of Sharif commission stressed the importance of English in Pakistan. It emphasized and accepted the status of English as one of the world's richest languages in respect to the vocation, which had a rich literature and good facilities to ensure speed in reporting the results of scientific and other researches (GoP, 1959).

In the view of above discussion, it can be safely conc-

cluded that study of literature and study of language can be mutually supportive. Literature is an ally to language teaching and not hostile as it is generally assumed. Different styles, forms, conventions, structures, constructions can be taught with the help of literary text. Another important reason for using literary text for the teaching language skills is to highlight the significances of literature. The research emphasizes on the point that the literary text can be used to teach language skills. Therefore, it is appropriate to conclude that a literary text is the best vehicle of teaching language skills. Students can enhance their grammatical compatibility through reading novel in the language class. As 'parts of speech' are major items in English language so novel will be used to teach parts of speech

Statement of the Problem

Grammar is considered as a dry and boring component of the English subject. That's why most of the teachers and students are not taking interest in learning and teaching grammar. Especially in Pakistan where Grammar Translation Method (GTM) is frequently used in classroom whereas other methods are not appreciated. So, the teaching parts of speech through literature are studied at elementary level.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study were as under:

1. To teach parts of speech through literature at elementary level
2. To identify parts of speech while reading literature at elementary level
3. To compare methods of teaching parts of speech with literature and without literature at elementary level

Hypothesis of the Study

The null hypothesis are given following;

- H_0 :1. There is no significant difference teaching parts of speech (noun) through literature and without literature.
 H_0 :2. There is no significant difference teaching parts of speech (pronoun) through literature and without literature.
 H_0 :3. There is no significant difference teaching parts of speech (adjective) through literature and without literature.
 H_0 : 4. There is no significant difference teaching parts of speech (verb) through literature and without literature.
 H_0 : 5. There is no significant difference teaching parts of speech (adverb) through literature and without literature.
 H_0 : 6. There is no significant difference teaching parts of speech through literature and without literature.

Significance of the Research

This study would invoke a spirit in the authorities running the schools to work in better way, hence improving especially the academic quality of the students. The more the institution improves, the more would be added to nation- building through education. The study will be very much important and useful for the English teachers as well as heads of the schools.

Delimitation

Keeping in view the constraints in term of finance and time, the study was delimited to:

1. First five kinds of part of speech i.e. Noun, Pronoun, Adjective, Verb and Adverb
2. Students of 8th class
3. Famous novel 'David Copperfield' by Charles Dicken

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research is an experimental research. Experimental research is commonly used in applied sciences but now a day it is equally considered as useful social sciences in language class room as well.

Population of the Study

The population of the research was taken from all 200 students of class 8th in HITEC Boys High School TaxillaCantt.

Sample of the Study

The sample of this research was 50 students of 8th class in HITEC Boys High School TaxillaCantt.

Research Instrument

A test was developed as research instrument for the research. Pre test and Post test were conducted from. The test was consisted of forty items, covering first five parts of speech. i.e. noun, pronoun, adjective, verb, and adverb. Pre-test and post-test were conducted from students.

Data Collection

Data were collected through pre test and post test. The tests were arranged to the control and experimental

Figure 1. Pie Chart of Parts of Speech

groups. The data were collected from these tests and coded the data for analysis.

Data Analysis

The data collected on each item of the pre test and post test were categorized.

Review of the Related Literature

The research entitled "Teaching Parts of Speech through Literature at Elementary Level" is a study of the parts of speech through literature which are influential for the achievement of the students.

1. According to Pound the Great literature is simply language charged with meaning to the utmost possible degree (Ezra Pound, How to Read, Part-1).
2. Broughton et al (1987) say in the allocation of the label 'great literature' to a literary work we cannot be making a judgment which is objective or factual
3. The teachers and professors who have the power to decide which books make up an English Literature syllabus reflects in their choices, and in the knowledge of the literature which they purvey, a fundamental structure of beliefs and interests which reflect the particular culture or section of society into which they were born and in which they grew up (Broughton, et al, 1987).
4. Literature is the best source of information about any age. If one wants to know about a language one has no other source but the literature of that language (Bloomfield, 1996).
5. According to Varghese, Every language has its grammar. Whether it is one's own mother tongue or a second-language that one is learning, the grammar of the language is important (Varghese, 1990).
6. Picking up grammar from ordinary conversation is an

attractive idea, but I don't know of any method that relies solely on acquisition in its pure form for the imparting of structural control.

6. Gowada (1982) says about importance of English, what we need to restore is the teaching of correct English as the essential craft through which all writing whether creative or not must be expressed. Children do need to learn the basic rules of grammar as well as what is regarded as good practice.

7. Obediat (1997) points out that 'Observation of my students has confirmed Salih's findings. My students tend to agree that literature helps them acquire a native like competence in English, express their ideas in good.

8. EnglishHall (1968) in his essay on language tells us that language is the institution whereby humans communicate and interact with each other by means of habitually used oral auditory arbitrary symbols.

9. Brooks (1969) expresses it, the study of culture is intimately related to both language and literature, to the former for ultimate meaning and to the latter for ultimate significance as a human art.

10. Finally, literature offers a special depth to language learning (Gregg & Pacheco, 1981), (Hargreaves, 1969), (Shumaker, 1975). Newton (1985) explains, one possible source of depth in language learning is literature.

Analysis of Data

The figure 1 shows percentage of control group is 43% whereas the result of experimental group is 57%. This result shows that there is an improvement in experimental group in the terms of parts of speech.

This bar graph shows over all comparison between two groups i.e. control group and experimental group. Through graph it is concluded that students of experimental group performed better than control group. There is significance

Figure 2. Bar Chart of Parts of Speech

improvement in all parts of speech which were taught through literature (Figure 2).

FINDINGS

On the basis of data analysis, the findings of the research were as under:

1. There was 48% value of control group whereas the value of experimental group was 52%. This result shows that there is an improvement in experimental group in the terms of noun through literature.
2. There was 42% value of control group whereas the value of experimental group was 58%. This result shows that there is an improvement in experimental group in the terms of pronoun through literature.
3. There was 38% value of control group whereas the value of experimental group was 62%. This result shows that there is an improvement in experimental group in the terms of adjective through literature.
4. There was 44% value of control group whereas the value of experimental group was 56%. This result shows that there is an improvement in experimental group in the terms of verb through literature.
5. There was 41% value of control group whereas the value of experimental group was 59%. This result shows that there is an improvement in experimental group in the terms of adverb through literature.
6. There was 43% value of control group whereas the value of experimental group was 57%. This result shows that there is an improvement in experimental group in the terms of parts of speech through literature.

CONCLUSIONS

The following conclusions were drawn on the basis of the findings of the research:

1. Experimental group was showing slightly good performance to identify the noun of the student.
2. Experimental group was showing a difference about the performance the student to identify the pronoun.
3. Experimental group was showing big difference to identify the adjective of the student.
4. Experimental group was showing a good performance to identify the student about verb.
5. Experimental group was showing well performance to identify the student about the adverb.
6. Experimental group was showing an improvement in learning of parts of speech.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations were drawn on the basis of the findings, review of related literature and observations made by researcher during this study; these may be helpful to teach parts of speech through literature.

1. The literature is useful for learning of the parts of speech.
2. The novels are interesting for the young students of the elementary levels.
3. The literature increases the information as well as vocabulary of the students.
4. The literature enhances the ability of the students so it must be part of their curriculum.

Further Area for Researches

More researches can be conducted on the Teaching Parts of Speech through Literature in English Language Classroom at Elementary Level of Students.

1. The present study was confined to the elementary classes. Similarly study can be conducted on the other

levels i.e. primary and high section.

1. The present study may be extended to the next parts of speech i.e. preposition, conjunctions, interjection and articles.
2. The present study may be extended to the other grammatical terms for examples tenses etc.

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